

ISic2739

I.Sicily inscription 2739

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Campobello di Mazara

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Selinunte, Deposit

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR109724

1. ε[]ε

2. λο

Edition: PHI333247

1. Εἰβέ-

2. λο̄.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284945

EDR 109724

EDCS 64400292

PHI 333247

Bibliography

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